

The Formation of Professional Identity in Volunteer Communities: A Social Construction Perspective

By: M Jabal Nur

Human Initiative
Email: nurmjabal@gmail.com

Submission date: September 2025

Accepted date: October 2025

Published in: October 2025

Abstract:

This study examines the social construction of professionalism through communicative practices within the Human Initiative Volunteer Energy (HIVE) South Sulawesi volunteer community, with a focus on the Remote Area Education Program in Pattuku Village. Using a descriptive qualitative approach with participatory observation and in-depth interviews, this study reveals how the meaning of professionalism is adapted from formal definitions to contextual communicative practices. The findings reveal five dimensions of adapted professionalism: boundless dedication, accountability to beneficiaries, creative adaptability, relational ethics, and continuous learning. This adaptation occurs through three patterns of communication—horizontal, vertical, and diagonal—which function as mechanisms of socialization and legitimization. This study contributes to the understanding of organizational communication by showing how the meaning of professionalism is adapted through communicative practices in the context of volunteering.

Keywords: social construction, professionalism, communicative practices, volunteering, rural education.

INTRODUCTION

Professionalism as a concept has undergone adaptations in meaning along with changes in social and organizational contexts. The conventional definition of professionalism, which refers to formal standards such as competence, quality, facilities, and infrastructure, and reliability (Siagian, 2009), faces challenges when applied in the context of volunteerism, especially in remote areas with limited resources. This study examines how the Human Initiative Volunteer Energy (HIVE) South Sulawesi volunteer community adapts the meaning of professionalism through communicative practices in the Remote Area Education Program in Pattuku Village.

Berger and Luckmann (2011), in their social construction theory, assert that reality is a social construction built through continuous symbolic interaction. In the context of professionalism, this means that the meaning of "being a professional" is not fixed, but instead constructed and reproduced through communicative practices within a

particular community. This is relevant for understanding how the concept of professionalism can adapt to the specific context of volunteer organizations.

The context of volunteering in remote areas presents unique challenges to mainstream conceptions of professionalism. Limited facilities, geographical challenges, and local community dynamics require a more contextual and flexible definition of professionalism. This study aims to reveal the mechanisms of social construction of professionalism through communicative practices in volunteer communities, as well as its implications for understanding professional identity and organizational communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Social Construction Theory in the Organizational Context

Berger and Luckmann (Peter L. Berger, 2011) explain that the social construction of reality occurs through three moments: externalization (self-expression in the social world), objectification (the achievement of reality that confronts individuals as external facts), and internalization (the reappropriation of objective reality into consciousness). In the context of professionalism, externalization occurs when volunteers engage in practices they consider professional. Objectification occurs when these practices become "the right way" in the community. Internalization occurs when the community's standards of professionalism become part of the individual identities of volunteers.

2. Communication in Communities of Practice

Wenger (Wenger, 1998) in Community of Practice Theory shows that professional learning is not only the transfer of technical knowledge but also the transformation of identity through participation in a community of practice. Communication facilitates legitimate peripheral participation, allowing newcomers to develop a professional identity through interaction with experienced practitioners gradually.

Organizational communication in this perspective is not merely the transmission of information but a practice that shapes shared meaning (Putnam & Nicotera, 2009). Horizontal, vertical, and diagonal communication patterns each have specific functions in shaping a collective understanding of professionalism.

3. Professionalism in the Context of Volunteering

Wilson (Wilson, 2000) defines voluntarism as activities in which time is freely given to benefit other people, groups, or organizations. This voluntary nature creates unique challenges for professionalism because there is no formal employment contract that defines performance standards.

Hustinx et al. (2010) identify that volunteer organizations face tension between maintaining volunteer spirit and ensuring quality performance. This requires a redefinition of professionalism that considers intrinsic motivation and value orientation rather than just technical and administrative aspects.

METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach that allows researchers to understand the phenomena of communication and volunteer professionalism in a natural context without manipulating variables (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The qualitative

approach was chosen because this study aims to explore the subjective meanings constructed by volunteers regarding professionalism and communication patterns in a non-profit organizational setting (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016).

The research locations were purposively determined in two main places: Pattuku Village, Parigi Village, Tinggimoncong District, Gowa Regency, as the program implementation location, and the South Sulawesi Human Initiative office on Jl. Puri Tata Indah No.36, Makassar, is the coordination center. The selection of these locations was based on accessibility and representativeness of the volunteer work context, both in the field and in organizational coordination (Patton, 2015).

This study adopted a social constructivist paradigm to understand how the meaning of professionalism and communication patterns are constructed within the volunteer community (Peter L. Berger, 2011). An interpretive phenomenological approach was used to explore *the lived experiences* of volunteers in building their professional identities within a philanthropic organization.

Research data was obtained from two main sources. Primary data was collected through in-depth interviews, observations, and direct documentation from informants. Secondary data was obtained from organizational documents, activity reports, operational guidelines, and digital communication documentation that supported data triangulation (Yin & Campbell, 2018).

Informants were selected using purposive sampling based on the criteria of involvement and knowledge relevant to the research focus (Palinkas et al., 2015). The research informants consisted of three categories with a total of 12 people:

Key informants: 4 people, including Abdur Rohim (Leader of HIVE South Sulawesi), Khaidir (Chair of HIVE), Swardi (Head of HI South Sulawesi Branch), and Yusuf (Principal of Pattuku Elementary School). Six primary informants were volunteers with varying degrees of experience, namely Afni and Risyad (teaching volunteers), Zainul (senior volunteer), Ibang (HIVE Education Division Coordinator), and other volunteers involved in the program. There were two supporting informants, representing students' parents and the local government, who provided the perspective of the beneficiaries.

Data collection was conducted through three primary methods in accordance with the characteristics of qualitative research. (Creswell, 2014). Observations were made to observe natural interactions between volunteers, communication patterns in coordination meetings, and program activities in the field. Semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted with each informant using flexible question guides that allowed for in-depth exploration of their experiences and perspectives (Seidman, 2019). Documentation included the collection of organizational documents, activity reports, program documentation, and photos, as well as limited access to digital communications, all with the informants' permission.

Each interview was audio recorded with the informant's written consent and documented in field notes to enrich the contextual data. The data collection process was carried out in stages, taking into account information saturation (Morse, 1995).

The research instruments were designed to be comprehensive yet straightforward in accordance with field conditions. The observation guide consisted of a checklist of activities, communication patterns, and observable indicators of professionalism. The semi-structured interview guide was organized in three stages: an opening to build rapport, a core to explore the research topic in depth, and a closing for clarification and additional information (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015).

The equipment used included smartphones for audio recording, field notebooks, and digital cameras for visual documentation. All instruments were designed to be portable and easy to use, given the limited infrastructure at the program location.

Data analysis used manual thematic analysis following the Braun and Clarke framework (Braun & Clarke, 2006) with the following stages: (1) familiarization with the data through repeated reading of transcripts and notes, (2) initial coding with a color coding system for theme categories, (3) identification of themes through grouping of similar codes, (4) review and refinement of themes, and (5) definition of final themes with support from direct quotes from informants.

The analysis process was conducted iteratively using the constant comparative method to ensure consistency of interpretation (Glaser & Strauss, 2009). The results were presented using rich narrative descriptions with direct quotations to give voice to the informants.

Data credibility was maintained through source triangulation by comparing the perspectives of various categories of informants, and method triangulation by combining observation, interviews, and documentation (Lincoln, 1990). Member checking was conducted by confirming initial interpretations with key informants to ensure the accuracy of the researcher's understanding (Birt et al., 2016).

Transferability is strengthened through detailed context descriptions (*thick description*) of the research setting, informant characteristics, and socio-cultural background (Geertz, 2004). Dependability is maintained through systematic documentation of the research process, while confirmability is ensured through the researcher's reflection on potential personal biases that may influence data interpretation (Tracy, 2010).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Contextual Adaptation of Professionalism

The research findings show the process of adapting the meaning of professionalism in the HIVE volunteer community. While Siagian (2008) defines professionalism through formal indicators such as ability, quality, facilities and infrastructure, and reliability. Remote area education volunteers create interpretations that are more appropriate to their context and limitations.

This adaptation occurs through communicative negotiation within the community. When Risyad states, "Being professional is not just about wearing neat clothes, but being willing to come even when you have a busy schedule and being willing to remain active," he communicates a redefinition of professionalism that emphasizes commitment and consistency rather than formal appearance.

This adaptation process does not reject conventional values of professionalism but adjusts them to the realities of working in remote areas. Volunteers still value quality standards and accountability, but operationalize them differently from formal organizational settings.

2. Five Dimensions of Contextual Professionalism

a. Unlimited Dedication as Emotional Commitment

The first dimension of contextual professionalism is boundless dedication, which reflects a high level of emotional engagement with the program. This dedication is communicated through a willingness to sacrifice personal comfort, flexibility in facing unexpected challenges, and persistence in achieving learning objectives.

Dedication is constructed through sharing stories about challenging experiences, recognizing peers for their extra efforts, and using visual documentation to show challenging working conditions. These communicative mechanisms create a norm that high dedication is expected behavior in the community.

b. Accountability to Beneficiaries

The finding that volunteers measure professionalism by "whether the children understand" indicates a shift from administrative accountability to outcome-based accountability. Volunteers are not only accountable to the organization but primarily to the children they teach.

The evening evaluation ritual serves as a communicative mechanism to reinforce this accountability. Volunteers consistently discuss student learning progress, identify areas for improvement, and commit to improvement the next day. This communication structure creates positive peer pressure to maintain the quality of learning.

c. Creative Adaptability in Problem-Solving

The construction of adaptability as a marker of professionalism reflects the reality of working in remote areas full of uncertainty. The ability to "find ways to keep lessons going even without a blackboard" is communicated as a core competence that distinguishes professional volunteers from amateurs.

Social learning mechanisms for adaptability include storytelling about creative solutions, peer observation and behavior modeling, collective brainstorming, and celebration of innovative practices. This shows that adaptability is a collective competence built through knowledge sharing within the community.

d. Relational Ethics in Community Integration

The inclusion of relational ethics as a professional requirement demonstrates an understanding that the program's success depends on acceptance from the local community. Ibang's statement that "you have to get to know the parents, participate in village events" indicates that relationship building is an essential professional skill.

Trust-building communication occurs through consistency between words and actions, transparency, reciprocity in relationship building, and respect for local knowledge. External legitimacy from the local community validates this relational ethics approach.

e. Continuous Learning as a Growth Mindset

The development of a learning mindset as a professional attribute demonstrates that volunteers see every experience as a learning opportunity. Reflexive communication practices include self-assessment, peer feedback, adaptation based on input, and documentation of the learning journey.

3. Communication Patterns as a Mechanism for Construction

a. Horizontal Communication: Peer Learning and Mutual Support

Horizontal communication patterns function as mechanisms for peer learning and mutual support. Collaborative two-way communication allows for the exchange of ideas and experiences without hierarchical barriers. Evening evaluation practices create a safe space for sharing challenges and solutions.

Horizontal communication also faces challenges in the form of differences in focus and priorities. Observations of WhatsApp groups show the need for moderation to maintain focus on program objectives and reduce distractions from irrelevant topics.

b. Vertical Communication: Standardization and Guidance

Vertical communication serves to ensure consistency in standards and provide guidance to volunteers. Top-down communication conveys policies, ethical standards, and organizational expectations. Bottom-up communication allows volunteers to provide feedback and contribute to decision-making.

This mechanism creates a balance between organizational control and volunteer autonomy. Leaders act as facilitators who ensure alignment with organizational values while providing flexibility in implementation.

c. Diagonal Communication: Cross-Functional Integration

Diagonal communication facilitates cross-functional and cross-level integration, which is particularly effective in the recruitment and initial training phases. Administrators can communicate directly with volunteers from various divisions to ensure effective coordination.

A gentle and persuasive approach in diagonal communication creates a welcoming atmosphere for new volunteers and facilitates their socialization into the organizational culture.

4. External Legitimacy and Social Capital

The construction of internal professionalism is validated by external recognition from the local community. Recognition from school principals, parents, and local government creates positive reinforcement that strengthens internal beliefs about the quality and relevance of their approach.

Professional behavior creates beneficial social capital on multiple levels: individual (skill development, networking, satisfaction), organizational (reputation, community support), and community (improved education quality, social cohesion). This shows that contextually constructed professionalism can produce positive outcomes for all stakeholders.

5. Resonance with Local Cultural Values

The concept of volunteer professionalism resonates with Indonesian cultural values, particularly cooperation and community orientation. The emphasis on collaboration, mutual support, and community integration reflects cultural continuity in the context of modern organizations.

HIVE has successfully combined quality and accountability standards with local values of relationship building and community service. This shows that the construction of professionalism does not occur in a vacuum but is embedded in a specific cultural context.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals that professionalism in the HIVE volunteer community is constructed through contextual adaptation, resulting in five dimensions: boundless dedication, accountability to beneficiaries, creative adaptability, relational ethics, and continuous learning. This adaptation occurs through three patterns of communication—horizontal, vertical, and diagonal—which function as mechanisms of socialization and legitimization.

These findings contribute to the understanding of organizational communication by showing that the meaning of professionalism can be adapted to specific contexts without losing its substance. This study also enriches Community of Practice Theory by showing how professional identity is formed through participatory communication in volunteer communities.

The practical implications of this research highlight the importance of developing communication mechanisms that facilitate the construction of contextually relevant professionalism. Volunteer organizations can learn from the HIVE approach in establishing realistic professional standards while maintaining quality and accountability.

The limitations of this study lie in its focus on one volunteer community and one specific program. Future research can explore the construction of professionalism in different volunteer contexts to develop a more comprehensive understanding of this phenomenon.

REFERENCES

- Birt, L., Scott, S., Cavers, D., Campbell, C., & Walter, F. (2016). Member Checking. *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(13), 1802–1811. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732316654870>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Qualitative Research & Research Design*. Pustaka Pelajar.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.

- Geertz, C. (2004). *Cultural Interpretation*. Rosdakarya.
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (2009). *The discovery of grounded theory: strategies for qualitative research*. Aldine Transaction: Made available through hoopla.
- HUSTINX, L., CNAAN, R. A., & HANDY, F. (2010). Navigating Theories of Volunteering: A Hybrid Map for a Complex Phenomenon. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 40(4), 410–434. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5914.2010.00439.x>
- Kvale, S., & Brinkmann, Svend. (2015). *Interviews: learning the craft of qualitative research interviewing*. Sage Publications.
- Lincoln, Y. S. (1990). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage.
- Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2016). *Qualitative research: a guide to design and implementation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Morse, J. M. (1995). The Significance of Saturation. *Qualitative Health Research*, 5(2), 147–149. <https://doi.org/10.1177/104973239500500201>
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful Sampling for Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis in Mixed Method Implementation Research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533–544. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y>
- Patton, M. Q. (2015). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Peter L. Berger, T. L. (2011). *Social Interpretation of Reality: A Treatise on the Sociology of Knowledge*. LP3ES.
- Putnam, L. L., & Nicotera, A. M. (2009). *Building Theories of Organization*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203891025>
- Seidman, I. (2019). *Interviewing as qualitative research: a guide for researchers in education and the social sciences*. Teachers College Press.
- Siagian, S. P. (2008). *Human resource management*. Bumi Aksara.
- Tracy, S. J. (2010). Qualitative Quality: Eight “Big-Tent” Criteria for Excellent Qualitative Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 16(10), 837–851. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800410383121>
- Wenger, E. (1998). *Communities of Practice*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CB09780511803932>
- Wilson, J. (2000). Volunteering. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 26(1), 215–240. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.soc.26.1.215>
- Yin, R. K., & Campbell, D. T. (2018). *Case study research and applications: design and methods*. SAGE Publications, Inc.